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AN INVESTIGATION ON VALUE ADDED MACHINES

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ABSTRACT

This paper is a review of research work of last few years on retrofitting. In this paper we are discussing the cost of retrofitting, monthly repairing and advantages of retrofitting. Machines cost and tool cost create big effects in manufacturing industries. Repairs and upgradations of machines and tools can help to reduce the overall cost of machines and there factors and can increase production rate.

Keywords: Retrofitting, Reconditioning, Automation.

INTRODUCTION

As we know that technologies have been developed day by day and very rapidly. In some recent years features are changing in manufacturing environment rapidly. In machining activities, big improvement is possible and the custom role of machine operators is being replaced more by the new intelligent controllers with new features. [1] This is only potential by upgrading the ageing machine tools to reconstruct exactness level, improving accessibility, enhancing output & facility. Retrofitting is the best potential answer to them. Retrofitting is direct to cost valuable transformation of obtainable workshop. [2]

Inspiration of Transformation

Inspiration of transformation comes from Olympus company of Noida since they have been started their organization they have accept that so many machine tools and plants has become outdated. Though there are tons several benefits of victimization new CNC machines of these machines cannot be discarded and replaced. For any trade replacement of machine tools by new CNC machines isn't doable one the difficulty of replacement versus renovation of ageing machine tools, the 4R's approach (Retire, Relegate, Renovation and Replacement) has been thought of. Renovation of ageing machine tools incorporates a important role to play in developing economic science like India thanks to following reasons:

1. Preventive value of latest instrumentality
2. Lack of adequate interchange resources for machinery import.
3. Deficiency of capital.
4. Inadequate information and no native support. [2]

Reconditioning

Reconditioning is method which can be defined as it is a process of planned orderly engineering energetically designed to refurbish all the utensils to its original performance and condition. It is a practical exercise which implement to restore their utensils work performance after long use to its true reliability and performance state. This process involve reconstruct to certain challenging areas in the machine like grinding and scrapping of guide ways to eliminate looseness due to wear and replacement of certain machine parts which is based upon the projected performance of the machine.[2]

Requirement of Reconditioning

Requirement of old utensils has a considerable role in to play in rising countries like India due to excessive costs of new utensils, need of sufficient foreign exchange support for machinery imports and shortage of assets. Once the validity of machine is over, its reliability decreases quickly and preparation of extra parts becomes a very hard job. The utensils have a very short life they can be fail without notice. Reconditioning or half-done restore tends to make stronger in a certain placed areas, but there is a risk of crash in these areas not reconditioned incessantly to remain. The strength is limited for the weakest part of the machine and the dependability of the machine is defined by the most not reliable device in the utensils and reconditioning or incomplete parts tend to delay the troubles for the future stage. [2]

Machine tool rejuvenation

CNC machines mechanical hardware life is almost 10 years with nonstop. If proper calibration and some minor repair is conducted on time such as changes of liners, alignment, pitch error and recoil correction are done the life of machine increase and it will contentedly doing their job for the subsequently 10 to 20 years. It is not levelheaded to piece of the machine even at the end of this session and since casting have free from all the stresses and become structurally more stable in fact castings are like wine-old is better than new in other words can say like a rice old is better than new. Therefore, they should be reconstruct for another 20 years of valuable life. CNC controllers have rapid development in electronics so lead to faster for outdated CNC controller. Therefore, the life of mechanical hardware is much better than the life of controllers. The genuine controller becomes pathetically lower to the newest ones within two years. Some of the controllers start off with completely different hidden versions. Therefore, spares for even a similar model aren't accessible or too costly. Once the CNC machines complete their helpful life or fail to satisfy the Cp and Cpk necessities, these will be given a recent lease of life through sure activities. These are observed as machine rejuvenation and might be 3 broad classes. [3]

- Retrofitting
- CNC controller upgradation
- Remanufacturing

Retrofitting

Retrofitting converts the traditional machine into a CNC machine by commutation its recent gear boxes and lead screws with ball screws and servomotors. Throughout 1983-98, usually retrofitted machines were solely little lathes and knee sort edge machines. Sometimes HMT AZ11 kind of boring machines were additionally retrofitted. These retrofits ne'er worked as full-fledged CNC machines. Compromises in accuracy and performance in these low price retrofits were accepted in those days. Customers ne'er took the danger of retrofitting on the far side this level. Throughout this era, the retrofitting market was dominated by

firms like Electronica, KEC and Techno four.

The present situation in retrofitting is considerably totally different, due to improved ability levels and client awareness. Customers area unit currently able to retrofit additional difficult machines like cylindrical grinders, borers, rotating shaft edge and grinding machines, shaft grinders, vertical turret lathes, roll turning lathes, tool and cutter grinders, roll grinders, gear cutting and grinding machines, etc. Not solely has the arrogance of the purchasers enlarged in retrofitting; they need additionally started hard to please productivity and accuracy from the retrofitted machines pretty much as good because the new machines. [3]

CNC controller up gradation

Upgradation of CNC controller involves replacement of the whole electrical and physical science of an existing NC/CNC machine. This is often the foremost economical answer among the 3 styles of rejuvenation since the mechanical hardware isn't attended. The flow of used machines into the country increased from 1995. In additional than ninetieth of those cases, the controllers have to be compelled to get replaced. moreover, technological devolution let alone lack of spares/ support necessitates replacement of the controllers with the most recent ones of constant build or a distinct one; this might be needed a minimum of each eight to ten years to use the total edges of the whole CNC system. There are variety of players within the market to hold out this upgradation. They're largely ex-employees of machine producing firms or the folks with maintenance background from huge producing firms [3]

Remanufacturing

Remanufacturing goes a step additional to repair or replace mechanical elements to the initial, "as new", manufactory specification. it's seemingly that the machine are going to be fully cleaned, inspected, disassembled, repaired and painted. All gas, hydraulic and electrical systems are going to be updated. The machine might also be changed or have mechanical accessories additional to re-purpose it for a replacement application much while not exception, remanufacturing can happen at the remanufacturer's website. Deciding whether or not to retrofit, construct or remanufacturer depends on the present condition of the machine and also the anticipated edges from the investment. Reviewing maintenance records and half yield statistics could facilitate perceive the state of the machines mechanical systems. A ball bar analysis may also be wont to diagnose mechanical issues. Retrofit, construct and remanufacturing corporations will be able to assess the present condition of the machine and suggest the suitable resolution. [4]

K. Khasgiwala, P.K. Basak, said that CNC retrofitting of machines for competitive advantage proceedings of LE. (I)Seminar command in town 1998, mentioned that reconditioning of recent instrumentality contains a significant role to play in developing countries like Asian country as a results of preventive costs of recent instrumentality, lack of adequate interchange resource for machinery imports and deficiency of capital. Once the generation of a machine is over, its trustworthiness decreases speedily and planning of spare parts becomes a tricky task. The components have associate occasional residual life and can fail whereas not a warning. Reconditioning or partial repair tends to strengthen certain set areas, but the possibility of breakdown in areas not fastened continuous to remain. [5]

S.N. Daga, said that CNC Retrofitting of standard machines, a price effective approach for small scale makers Vision 1994-95, Indian Institute of Business Engineers, mentioned that to bring CNC operation into operative, it is not necessary to travel for a

latest CNC machine. it's usually achieved by incorporating CNC choices as an example DRO CNC system. PLC's, thirstier drives etc. into exiting ageing typical machine. Owning of recent instrumentality contains a significant role to play in developing countries like Asian country as a results of preventive costs of recent instrumentality, lack of adequate interchange resource for machinery imports and deficiency. [6]

K.P Karunakaran and S Meyyappan, said that Today's a large style of CNC machines unit used for metal cutting, sheet operating, nontraditional machining, inspection, etc. in conjunction with the developments in drives, sensors and controls of CNC machines, there are tremendous growth in associated units like cutting tools and CNC programming software system. several industries are reluctant to form immense investments in new CNC machines. This is often owing to the very fact that totally different levels of automation through rejuvenation of previous machines area unit out there to them with different price implications and commensurable advantages. Metal operating largely involves cutting and forming mistreatment each typical also as CNC machines.

Given this market size, the will of machine users to reinforce the machine's life & capabilities, and therefore the machine building skills on the market among the country, the machine rejuvenation trade is poised to grow during a massive approach. [3]

The approximate cost of retrofitting various machines is given in Table 1

Cost of retrofitting conventional machine into a CNC machine Table 1	
Type of machine	Cost of retrofitting in percentage of new machine
Lathe: up to 8" chuck diameter	120 - 130%
Lathe: 12" to 24" chuck diameter	80 - 100%
Lathe: >20" chuck diameter and >3,000 mm between centres	40 - 60%
Knee type milling machine	120 - 130%
VTL: up to 1,600 mm chuck diameter	40 - 60%
VTL: 4,000-6,300 mm chuck diameter	30 - 40%
Crankshaft/ Camshaft grinders	30 - 40%
<p>Note for Tables 1 and 2:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ☐ Cost of used machine is not considered in the percentage calculations. To get the correct comparison with new machine, add the cost of used machine ☐ For comparison, government taxes and levies are not considered ☐ The above percentages show the conversion cost when compared to the new machine cost 	

The approximate cost of controller upgradation is given in Table 2

Cost of CNC controller upgradation and remanufacturing Table 2		
Type of machines	Cost in percentage of new machines	
	CNC Controller upgradation	CNC remanufacturing
CNC lathe: up to 8" chuck diameter	50%	90 - 110%
CNC lathe: 12" to 24" chuck diameter	30 - 40%	50 - 60%
CNC lathe: >20" chuck diameter and >3,000 mm between centres	15 - 20%	25 - 30%
Small VMC: up to 400 mm x 630 mm table	60 - 70%	90 - 110%
Larger VMC: above 400 mm x 630 mm table	30 - 40%	50 - 60%
Small HMC: up to 500 mm x 500 mm table	60 - 70%	90 - 110%
Large HMC: above 500 mm x 500 mm table	20 - 30%	30 - 40%
Floor borer	15 - 20%	20 - 30%
Crankshaft/ Camshaft grinders	10 - 20%	20 - 30%

Chaudhary. A. et.al., [2] reported that due to rising ideas like economic process and liberalization these days client have option to amendment their demands frequently therefore market lifetime of product reduces. Conventional aging producing machine tools cannot meet these necessities. So as to sustain competition and existence in world market, Indian producing industries got to upgrade its technology for its survival and conjointly to sharpen its future competitive edge. This is often potential by upgrading the senescent machine tools to revive accuracy level, improving availability, enhancing productivity & capability. CNC Retrofitting may be a price effective technique of upgrading capabilities of existing machine tools. Suggestions relating to future work are incorporated hereby practicability of retrofitting is analyzed by means that of case study.

Materials of machines: [2]

Economic comparison for machine performance calculation. Number of working hours/year = $(2 \times 8) \times 6 \times 50 = 4800$ hours $I =$ interest rate = 20% per annum, $S =$ Salvage value = 0.1 x capital cost
Interest taken as 20% per annum.

TABLE 3

	Initial Cost	Annual maintenance and other cost	Hourly labour cost
16 C Conv.	18 lakhs	Rs. 2.1 lakhs	Rs. 80
Upgraded CNC	45 lakhs	Rs. 2.4 lakhs	Rs. 80
New CNC	90 lakhs	Rs. 5.0 lakhs	Rs. 80

Data before upgradation

Total working hours = 4800 hours

Down Time = 1050 hours

(i) Availability = $(4800-1050)/4800 = 78.0\%$ (ii) Up time ratio = $(4800-1050)/4800 = .78$

(iii) Down time ratio = $1050 / 4800 = 0.22$

Data obtained after upgradation Total working hours= 4800 hours Down Time = 185 hours

(i) Availability = $(4800-185)/4800 = 96.0\%$ (ii) Up time ratio = $(4800-185)/4800 = .96$ (iii)

Down time ratio = $96 / 4800 = 0.04$

Fig 1. Cycle time reduction

Fig 2. % Availability

Fig 3. of components/ year

Fig 4. Cost of machine

Kareem. B. et al., said that importance of machine tools and maintenance:

The machine tools are ever present instruments of recent producing and that they shaped the bases for industrial development. Unbelievable dynamism in machine tools development needs an assessment on supported utilization stage, and determines the scope of work for economic choice of machine tools. The factors that were thought of paramount for the assessment enclosed labor skillfulness (age, sex, experience); maintainability (number of breakdown and preventive maintenance stoppage, maintenance quality, available machine hours); practicality (frequency of use, demand rate); and level of technological innovation/acquisition as associated with some factors enclosed rate of turnover, customer satisfaction, reduction in value and raw materials. Forty structured questionnaires were administered among the selected machine tools industries in Federal Republic of Nigeria to gather knowledge on the afore-stated factors, among others. Descriptive applied mathematics method supported percentages was used for evaluating the performances of the known factors. Maintainability performance was resolute mistreatment maintenance quantitative relation supported percentage stoppage of known machine tools together with shaping machine, milling and

drilling machines. The results obtained showed that lack of expertise and preparation of personnel had militated against effective utilization of machine tools in Nigerian industries. Speedy pace of technological innovation/acquisition in the machine tools industries had been hindered by merchandise importation and high price of fuel. [7]

Table 4 shows Monthly Repair Complexity of Machine Tools
Table 4

Machine Tools Repair	Model	Engineering Characteristics	Complexity (Hr/month)
Gear hobber	5K32A	500 X 8Module	12
Centre lathe	LB-20	410D X 1000L	9
Centre lathe	LB-17	410D X 1000L	9
Centre lathe	RM65	350D X 750L	7
Radial drill	3B724	75D	18
Surface grinder	7M37	2000 X4000 able	30
Shaper	7M37	1000 Stroke	12
Shaper	7M450	1000 Stroke	12
Slotter	2DV90	500 Stroke	10
Universal milling	M3V	330 X 1400 Table	15
Vertical milling	PRATAP	320 X 1260 Table	13
Vertical drill	M2V	25D	14
Vertical Milling	M2V	310 X 1100 Table	11
Centre lathe	LB-20	410D X 1000L	9
Centre lathe	1622	550D X 2500L	13
Centre lathe	TR70B	680D X 1500L	14
Centre lathe	TR70B	680D X 2000L	14
Centre lathe	TR90	900D X 1500L	20
Vertical boring	2K300	2600D X 1600H	51
Radial drill	RM65	75D	18
Horizontal boring	PRTSN	125D Spindle	31
Planer	7210	1000 X 3200 Table	31
Planer	7212	1250 X 4000 Table	35
Types of production Percentage (Hr/month)	Percentage Stoppage	monthly repair complexity	Total repair complexity
Unit production	1.0	50	406
Series production	1.5	67	609
Mass production	2.0	100	812

Fig 5. **Monthly Repair Complexity of Machine Tools**

This survey would positively facilitate the producing industries to develop a machine for improvement of production.

There are some factors which always affect on machine which have assume from other journal.

1) By introducing automatic tool turret, hydraulically operated tall stock, changed hinumeric CNC controller and servo drives, choice of tool, speed and feed are performed mechanically per instruction given in program. This stuff result in dramatic decrease in cycle time three hours to 1.00 hour. Fatigue to employee is reduced and his duty is proscribed to loading and unloading, getting into program. By retrofitting high performance ball crews in situ of typical lead screw transmission potency drastically improved with slippery contact replaced by rolling contact.

2) During Upgradation defective elements area unit either repaired or replaced to bring back original accuracy. This results in lesser down time, higher machine accuracy, that successively increase availability from seventy eight to ninety six the troubles. Accuracy's area unit virtually kind of like those of Original CNC machine

TABLE 5

Ball Screw	Lead Screw		
96%	60%	LINEAR	EFFICIENCY
96%	40%	ROTATING	EFFICIENCY

- 3) AC servo motors, drives iatrogenic higher speed upto a thousand rate while not drop torsion.
- 4) correct positioning, precession feed earned through PLC controlled turret provide higher accuracy's, higher repeatability, thus lesser rejection and her quality.
- 5) Cycle time reduction, top quality with lower rejection makes price of the assembly significantly lower.
- 6) Chip conveyors, machine enclosure, connected for safety of employee enhance time saving. Centralized automatic lubrication system improves tool life and facilitates extended Operation.
- 7) By incorporating machine within the turret for drilling, and grinding we will more improve productivity.
- 8) Hydraulic chuck, automatic job handling added to more improve, productivity.
- 9) C-axis arrangement can improve capability of upgraded machine to machine involved complicated components. With the assistance of Trojan horse it's terribly straightforward to determine the practicability of a machine for Upgradation. we've conjointly analyzed the value effectiveness of upgraded machine at par with CNC still as standard machines. [2]

Result

From the literature review I got the information regarding approximate cost of retrofitting of various machines, approximate cost of controller upgradation and monthly repair complexity of machine tools and also seen some factors which are really responsible for cost and maintenance of retrofitting. Different research are available in retrofitting but in my survey I investigate that many papers based on cost either calculated by software or machining activity but there is no any paper or research are available which can based on taking decision whether should go for retrofitting or purchase a new machine and my objective is how to take a decision whether should go for retrofitting, purchase a new machine or maintain a machine presently available.

TABLE 6

	16C Conv.	Upgraded Machine	New CNC
Machine hour rate (Rs.)	232.24	327.39	579
Machining time (in hours)	3.00	1.00	.916
Cost of machining (Rs) Capital	696.72	327.39	530.36
Cost (lakhs) Number of	18	45	90
Component produced/year *	1500	4500	5241

Conclusion

The purpose of this study was to obtain information about the cost which is involved in retrofitting of the machines tools and to identify other parameters which will decide whether we should go for retrofitting of the machine or to purchase a new machine. This information can be obtained from the survey of various industries which has taken the decision of retrofitting of machines and what parameters they have decided for this. The aim of this study is to optimize the capital investments on these activities and factors which are responsible for the cost of retrofitting.

Retrofitting may be upgradation technique that is use for convert previous machine in to updated machines. Based on the results, it's straightforward to require any selections. How ever knowledge that is use terribly sophisticated and combination of previous knowledge and new knowledge it's administered much.

The results are obtained have evidenced that retrofitting is incredibly price effective technique for enhancing productivity, availableness and rising performance level. With appropriate and economical application of automation, worth addition takes place and increases the performance of retrofitted machines. Tailored retrofit makes most re-use of existing instrumentality and is thus additional economical than an entire new installation. With the likelihood to sequence the retrofit installation, service interruptions will be decreased.

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